

Ostsee VII Fpl 92, Meklenburg-Vorpommern, Germany

by

Aoife Daly, Ph.D.

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Ten samples from wreck found in Greifswald Bay were analysed dendrochronologically, to determine their date and provenance. The results of this analysis is described in this report.

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and for the calculation of the t-value ("t-test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are used. The analysis has been aided by input from Anne Crone, AOC Archaeology Group, Edinburgh and Karl-Uwe Heußner, Deutsches Archäologisches Institut.

In the interest of open access to data and to enable researchers to utilise this material in the future, and indeed date the material that is as yet not dated, all measurements are printed in the catalogue.

Ostsee VII Fpl 92

A total of 10 timbers, all made from *Quercus sp.*, oak, are analysed dendrochronologically. Five of the samples are from planks from the wreck, and all these are dated. The remaining samples are from the ship's keel and from framing timbers. While the tree-ring curves from four of these timbers can cross-match between each other, it has not been possible to date these. One treenail, that remained still attached to one of the dendrochronology samples, has been analysed to determine species. This treenail is made from *Pinus sp.*, pine.

	Z054006a	Z054002a	Z0540059	Z054003a	Z054004a
Z054006a	*	8,62	8,23	6,09	8,34
Z054002a	8,62*		12,81	9,17	9,76
Z0540059	8,23	12,81*		10,54	9,72
Z054003a	6,09	9,17	10,54*		9,67
Z054004a	8,34	9,76	9,72	9,67*	

Table 1. Ostsee VII, Mönchgut, Fpl 92, correlation between the tree-ring curves from the planks.

The planks

Table 1 shows the internal correlation (t-value) between the tree-ring curves from the five planks. These five are averaged to form a mean curve (Z054M001) that spans 214 years. This mean curve is dated, and covers the period AD 1235 to 1448. All the plank samples have sapwood, and one has bark edge preserved. The bark ring is completely formed which means that the tree was felled in **winter or early spring AD 1448-49**. It is probable that all the trees used to make the planks were felled at this time (see fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Ostsee VII Fpl 92. The chronological position of the dated samples.

The frames and keel

Table 2 shows the internal correlation (t-value) between the tree-ring curves from three framing timbers and the keel. As can be seen by the high t-values, these timbers cross-match internally. The tree-ring curves from these four timbers are averaged to form a mean curve (Z054M002) and this spans 154 years. It has not been possible to date this material. This mean curve does not cross-match with the mean from the planks, and therefore most probably these trees come from a different region.

	Z0540109	Z0540019	Z0540089	Z054007a
Z0540109	*	6,78	4,97	3,31
Z0540019	6,78*	*	6,98	5,04
Z0540089	4,97	6,98*	*	8,07
Z054007a	3,31	5,04	8,07*	*

Table 2. Ostsee VII, Mönchgut, Fpl 92, correlation between the tree-ring curves from three framing timbers and the keel.

The relative position of four undated tree-ring curves is shown in fig. 2. One of the floor timbers has sapwood and bark edge preserved, and was felled in winter.

Fig. 2. Ostsee VII Fpl 92. The relative position of the undated samples.

One frame timber, bodenwrange 63, contained just 25 tree-rings. This timber has far too few rings for dendrochronological analysis, but was measured nevertheless, so that it can be included in the dendrochronological dataset for future possible research.

12th October 2010

As mentioned above, a treenail still attached to one of the frames is made from *Pinus sp.*, pine.

Filenames	-	-	Z054M001	
-	Start	dates	AD 1235	
-	Dates	end	AD 1448	
0M040004	AD 1156	AD 1597	9,69	Baltic 1 (Hillam and Tyers, 1995)
0075M001	AD 1113	AD 1463	7,72	Vejdyb (Daly 1997)
lskn_a1	AD 1153	AD 1372	6,53	Skanor cog (Marek Krapiec pers comm)
StCrux27	AD 1144	AD 1388	5,94	York St Crux Church (Tyers pers comm.)
0628021M	AD 1256	AD 1443	5,90	Torun Joh K (Wazny pers comm.)
se613m01	AD 1197	AD 1464	5,00	Hull Blaydes Staithe (Tyers pers comm.)
0M040005	AD 1257	AD 1615	4,94	Baltic 2 (Hillam and Tyers, 1995)
P0011009	AD 1103	AD 1403	4,85	Copper Ship Wainscot (Wazny pers comm.)
0207M002	AD 1200	AD 1402	4,64	Dokøen vrag 3 (Bonde & Eriksen 2002)
02071M01	AD 1126	AD 1414	4,56	Dokøen Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001)
P734001M	AD 1246	AD 1412	4,52	Bransk (Wazny pers comm.)
2129M001	AD 1124	AD 1399	4,48	Niels Hemmingsensgade barrel (Daly 2000)
B019M002	AD 1374	AD 1574	4,37	Helsingør Kulturværft two barrels (Daly 2009)
Z005M002	AD 1177	AD 1356	4,14	Bølevraget Norge 4 beams (Daly & Nymoen 2006)
HMC_T165	AD 1078	AD 1369	4,11	Hull coffin boards, Yorkshire, Baltic data (Tyers 1998)
0670108	AD 725	AD 1985	4,05	Gdansk (Wazny pers comm.)
B0111m01	AD 1201	AD 1417	3,65	Kompagnist, næstved polish barrel (Daly 2007)

Table 3. Ostsee VII Fpl 92. Result of the correlation between the mean curve for the planks from the ship (Z054M001) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies are given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

As can be seen from the table of t-values achieved between the mean curve for the planks and master and site chronologies for oak from Northern Europe (table 3) the highest correlation is with a chronology called “Baltic 1”. This chronology is constructed from tree-ring data from oak panel paintings. These panels were a very popular commodity in Western Europe, and were derived from trees from the regions around the Southern Baltic Sea. Particularly in the period from around the mid 14th to mid 15th centuries we see a quite large amount of panels, planks and boards in the dendrochronological record, that represent this extensive trade in timber products. The data that the planks from this ship match best with are from other ship’s planks, barrels, and decorative panels found in Denmark, Sweden, Norway England etc, all of which were made using Southern Baltic oaks.

The tree-ring curves from the framing and keel timbers from the Fpl 92 wreck, as mentioned above, do not cross-match with the curves from the planks. They do however cross-match well with each other. This leads to the conclusion that the frames and keel are from trees from a quite different region than the planks. Availability of new chronologies will most probably enable the dating of this material, some time in the future.

Literature

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12th October 2010

Catalogue

Catalogue format:

Filename
 Title and sample number
 Tree species (QUSP = *Quercus sp.*, oak, PISY = *Pinus sp.*, pine, PCAB = *Picea abies*, spruce) and number of years measured
 Chronological position of the tree-ring curve
 Number of sapwood years, presence of bark
 Felling date
 The measurements start at the innermost preserved ring

Z0540019

Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 kiel 85 SN22313
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 140 years length
 Undated
 0 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 148.78 Sensitivity 0.17

135	163	189	156	132	155	129	147	168	195
183	208	217	198	242	176	153	156	300	241
151	99	95	68	71	87	86	107	159	211
199	142	135	167	176	198	161	119	113	166
173	166	122	109	79	106	116	149	168	171
137	125	107	147	179	201	259	182	196	128
154	110	95	102	124	195	127	133	260	229
270	220	240	210	134	146	126	184	208	184
186	159	145	137	168	164	146	153	190	158
162	159	117	88	124	116	100	115	124	135
160	163	165	142	126	140	98	125	123	123
121	130	138	130	129	123	154	182	130	133
108	117	126	112	121	135	141	141	171	175
165	146	103	114	87	79	105	85	104	89

Z054002a

Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planke 7 8 117 SN22314
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 173 years length
 Dated AD 1276 to AD 1448
 14 sapwood rings and winter bark surface
 Average ring width 139.18 Sensitivity 0.22
 Interpretation AD 1448-49 winter

199	180	172	242	226	167	110	278	222	196
237	326	290	257	163	147	88	201	195	242
185	167	156	169	109	220	230	198	177	115
146	99	106	155	162	130	265	215	183	125
157	122	136	147	155	211	163	145	130	151
173	157	158	166	166	184	195	111	149	161
227	99	108	129	181	163	115	89	86	101
114	114	130	148	136	225	128	118	96	69
83	69	104	150	149	133	158	211	117	109
217	153	93	99	85	153	124	128	98	160
127	127	144	95	127	160	123	123	184	149
98	135	127	108	126	102	175	148	142	92
178	146	168	149	160	134	89	81	98	98
158	149	135	105	107	140	138	116	93	106
88	124	119	105	130	144	135	77	69	73
67	63	80	105	101	81	74	78	72	74
94	94	99	79	111	115	109	125	106	90
122	90	70							

12th October 2010

Z054003a

Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planke 82 119 SN22315

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 210 years length

Dated AD 1235 to AD 1444

20 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 122.40 Sensitivity 0.21

Interpretation AD 1445-54

90	95	74	45	73	93	107	136	134	132
202	205	158	121	200	125	153	178	210	145
237	205	178	146	175	124	97	193	164	152
141	82	90	103	154	141	223	139	209	173
168	155	114	121	97	75	121	92	157	129
135	150	193	154	163	147	147	77	118	91
153	102	76	123	207	189	150	145	173	119
91	100	72	96	125	120	135	175	168	121
88	116	103	132	134	134	155	114	126	103
133	128	95	94	94	100	128	115	82	92
134	151	77	79	123	114	184	146	86	79
113	124	132	141	110	131	126	95	106	85
69	76	59	82	129	113	98	139	166	88
87	149	161	119	74	98	105	94	128	105
136	108	99	127	105	83	98	116	118	125
123	97	117	135	129	102	107	123	136	174
109	181	136	127	139	131	133	100	84	68
78	111	128	124	134	135	132	121	119	90
110	122	125	133	117	134	143	146	95	77
81	80	67	71	92	95	73	96	75	85
104	117	95	87	82	99	89	116	205	169

Z054004a

Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planke 5 SN22316

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 202 years length

Dated AD 1243 to AD 1444

9 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 122.76 Sensitivity 0.22

Interpretation AD 1445-65

150	152	199	192	220	194	298	128	233	227
209	145	216	204	192	156	184	139	82	171
94	115	191	125	95	141	178	155	303	187
232	206	183	142	127	116	136	144	148	102
199	151	167	133	184	204	213	209	169	108
122	96	116	127	131	178	137	112	104	131
140	97	91	77	77	148	119	118	104	172
262	160	95	132	171	112	131	95	123	101
130	145	169	174	117	117	112	105	157	151
112	149	137	151	94	78	105	132	210	132
108	105	97	110	149	114	92	125	124	125
89	80	72	90	65	89	95	119	107	94
149	89	106	192	184	84	80	81	111	77
101	86	100	97	98	112	96	104	193	93
120	108	111	88	130	129	86	91	87	106
121	140	104	139	102	133	108	98	114	67
71	69	64	82	88	88	78	75	92	82
95	64	92	78	74	87	87	79	117	98
75	77	80	75	67	52	86	85	69	65
71	61	73	78	97	69	76	63	87	93
84	86								

12th October 2010

Z0540059

Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planke 6 SN22317

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 206 years length

Dated AD 1239 to AD 1444

9 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 121.23 Sensitivity 0.21

Interpretation AD 1445-65

112	134	187	200	211	176	261	248	200	166
245	109	210	195	250	149	178	276	243	203
278	243	129	179	189	213	205	175	79	146
175	233	252	197	195	183	203	155	133	133
80	74	80	59	125	149	130	132	167	174
132	127	130	57	126	72	86	68	73	75
82	83	108	146	108	91	77	145	99	68
106	87	90	135	175	104	79	97	98	96
128	114	111	110	143	133	221	158	135	135
168	173	163	159	109	152	151	223	100	146
122	179	198	131	75	96	118	107	111	97
126	144	159	108	106	110	62	72	63	77
124	144	107	131	216	129	108	188	193	96
101	100	130	113	144	111	159	134	151	106
97	99	127	93	97	107	89	77	96	93
104	95	100	133	105	105	96	142	97	104
113	88	92	69	57	65	71	90	104	85
71	78	96	111	91	82	79	77	92	77
76	70	85	100	57	64	54	49	47	49
49	53	54	57	47	56	44	73	63	58
48	54	46	47	61	52				

Z054006a

Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planke 81 116 SN22318

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 162 years length

Dated AD 1284 to AD 1445

7 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 158.81 Sensitivity 0.20

Interpretation AD 1448-68

226	240	193	185	158	230	162	163	84	81
68	62	99	91	105	84	76	137	177	157
163	140	121	81	90	140	134	142	305	327
186	195	226	261	246	281	278	221	198	218
172	192	190	105	113	127	145	182	202	140
213	184	232	107	95	95	113	142	137	97
100	103	129	144	127	121	122	127	135	147
175	91	113	79	79	109	157	142	209	226
147	251	418	308	306	217	157	258	147	190
169	140	114	172	164	154	171	201	151	151
181	176	135	180	184	174	182	167	203	204
209	144	236	178	256	205	209	176	132	130
85	107	141	162	188	156	152	164	166	199
202	204	196	187	122	129	99	171	154	105
120	111	98	89	110	127	109	102	156	106
126	83	141	181	121	107	94	121	123	156
158	104								

12th October 2010

Z054007a

Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 bodenwrange 54 56 SN22319

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 118 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 107.37 Sensitivity 0.18

151	141	135	132	123	118	101	58	53	68
61	70	73	82	48	53	47	55	47	70
69	62	73	104	101	97	113	104	114	96
85	83	69	89	76	76	69	68	111	139
135	127	149	191	172	197	228	141	209	144
119	75	75	71	114	128	91	101	160	135
169	177	162	132	77	59	80	135	163	171
141	147	147	143	192	256	115	140	192	166
134	129	76	67	74	66	64	77	74	115
134	146	158	131	131	131	120	152	108	82
88	97	100	73	61	66	82	68	53	49
52	62	68	57	61	91	75	88		

Z0540089

Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 bodenwrange spant 53 SN22320

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 120 years length

Undated

16 sapwood rings and winter bark surface

Average ring width 63.13 Sensitivity 0.20

91	97	85	44	36	56	46	76	42	77
56	76	44	77	76	96	92	82	75	69
74	71	94	73	75	52	56	43	39	48
82	82	75	57	117	83	123	114	120	130
53	59	81	97	126	100	85	73	81	73
103	113	65	61	72	65	47	56	41	38
42	42	33	52	40	59	61	84	87	75
71	72	61	71	60	63	93	63	74	51
43	53	85	47	39	37	30	34	36	36
39	48	55	58	54	52	46	44	37	34
38	36	36	34	44	35	37	29	39	48
43	67	55	52	65	59	54	59	57	38

Z0540099

Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 bodenwrange 63 SN22321

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 25 years length

Undated

2 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 270.84 Sensitivity 0.19

296	345	223	276	153	165	173	212	174	195
294	274	218	219	287	271	312	289	232	219
299	428	500	406	311					

12th October 2010

Z0540109

Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 konsl-teil 29 SN22322

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 111 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 136.06 Sensitivity 0.23

45	27	33	38	20	67	15	32	53	64
136	113	118	123	135	103	92	86	80	86
119	123	104	134	58	120	108	170	138	123
104	109	80	127	149	165	202	176	175	166
126	105	76	114	140	221	190	128	205	186
241	251	278	282	134	147	168	216	227	185
269	205	194	157	206	169	149	184	223	187
158	142	78	55	86	113	105	102	102	121
131	165	151	146	162	156	125	99	145	140
153	149	158	146	127	125	147	153	119	141
149	120	129	154	108	149	126	163	181	133
112									

Treenail

 Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 treenail, *Pinus sp.*, pine.

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	Conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra start	extra end	Interpretation / felling
Z0540019	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 kiel 85 SN22313	140			O	C	-	-	-	H1	Undated
Z054002a	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planke 7 8 117 SN22314	173	AD 1276	AD 1448	R	G	14	winter	-	-	AD 1448-49 winter
Z054003a	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planke 82 119 SN22315	210	AD 1235	AD 1444	R	G	20	-	-	S1	AD 1445-54
Z054004a	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planke 5 SN22316	202	AD 1243	AD 1444	R	G	9	-	-	S1	AD 1445-65
Z0540059	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planke 6 SN22317	206	AD 1239	AD 1444	R	G	9	-	-	S1	AD 1445-65
Z054006a	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planke 81 116 SN22318	162	AD 1284	AD 1445	R	G	7	-	-	S1	AD 1448-68
Z054007a	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 bodenwrange 54 56 SN22319	118			O	F	-	-	-	H1	Undated
Z0540089	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 bodenwrange spant 53 SN22320	120			O	C	16	winter	-	-	Undated
Z0540099	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 bodenwrange 63 SN22321	25			O	C	2	-	-	S1	Undated
Z0540109	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 konsl-teil 29 SN22322	111			O	C	-	-	-	H1	Undated
Z054m001	Ostsee VII planks 5 timber mean	214	AD 1235	AD 1448							
Z054m002	Ostsee VII floor etc 4 timber mean	154									Undated

Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.
 Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 - 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.